

Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium in Steel using 4(2-Thiazolylazo)-Resorcinol and Hydroxylamine

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SOME heterocyclic azo dyes have been used for estimation of vanadium. They are very sensitive although less selective. One such dye, 4(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR), forms a ternary complex with vanadium(V) in presence of hydroxylamine¹. It is known that the colour reactions involving PAR are very much sensitive to pH of the reacting solutions and in fact the concentration of vanadium necessary to form a complex with the azo dye is determined at each pH value. For analytical use, PAR is known to form two stable coloured complexes in presence of hydroxylamine at pH 3-4 with λ_{\max} at 540 nm and $\epsilon = 1.72 \times 10^4$; and pH 7-9 with λ_{\max} at 500 nm and $\epsilon = 3.9 \times 10^4$. The present work describes one such interesting colour reaction involving an analogous azo dye containing a thiazolyl group, viz, 4(2-thiazolylazo)resorcinol (TAR) and hydroxylamine. The determination of small amounts of vanadium in steel is based on the formation of an intensely coloured three component complex of vanadium with TAR and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acid medium.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The reagent TAR was prepared and purified according to literature method² and a 0.025% (w/v) TAR solution was prepared in distilled water. A stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared from A.R. grade ammonium metavanadate in distilled water and was standardised for vanadium content volumetrically³. The stock solution was further diluted to give 5 μg vanadium per ml of solution. Elico digital pH meter model LI-120 was used for pH determination. Elico spectrophotometer model CL-24 with 1 cm cell was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure: A suitable aliquot (0.2 to 2 ml) of vanadium(V) solution was taken in a 10 ml stoppered cylinder, 2 ml borate buffer (pH 9.2) was added followed by 0.4 ml TAR reagent and 1 ml 1 M hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution. The mixture was diluted to the mark and heated on water bath for 5-10 min to ensure complete reaction. It was then cooled and the absorbance of the reddish yellow coloured complex was measured at 550 nm.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium is known to be present in the pentavalent state¹ in all the three component complexes formed with PAR and hydroxylamine. It was also established that the three component complexes absorb to a greater extent than the two component one and are also more stable to the addition of many other anions. An examination of the absorption curves of the TAR complexes at various acidities showed that over a pH range 3.7 to 4.8, the three component system forms a stable complex at pH 4.4 with λ_{\max} at 550 nm. The formation of a stable complex at this pH has been used to develop a sensitive method for determination of vanadium. The colour system is stable for 45 min at room temp. and obeys Beer's law over the range 0.1 to 1.0 μg of vanadium per ml of the solution. The molar absorptivity value (ϵ) calculated from Beer's law plots is 20,360 at 550 nm, and the corresponding Sandell's sensitivity⁴ is 0.0025 μg vanadium/cm².

The effect of foreign ions in the determination of 5 μg of vanadium(V) in 10 ml solution was studied. It was observed that it suffered interference mainly from Fe(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pb(II). EDTA also seriously interfered in the reaction. The tolerance limit of other ions in (μg) is oxalate (25), tartrate (20), acetate (2000), phosphate (50), fluoride (N.I.), Mn(II) (100), Ba (2000), W(VI) (200).

The ratio of metal to reagent (TAR) in presence of excess hydroxylamine hydrochloride was determined by Job's⁵ and mole ratio⁶ method. In both the experiments the ratio of vanadium to reagent (TAR) was found to be 1 : 1. In the light of the studies carried out in a three component system involving PAR, it is assumed that an 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex is formed in this case also. Attempts are being made to isolate the solid complex and establish its composition.

Application of the method in BCS steels :

0.5 g vanadium steel was dissolved in 1 : 1 HNO₃. The hydrated tungstic acid was filtered. The oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling. Then the major quantity of iron was extracted using diisopropyl ether. Chromium and manganese in the acid layer were oxidised by boiling with potassium chlorate. The residual iron and vanadium were precipitated by 1 : 1 NH₄OH. The precipitate was dissolved in minimum quantity of 1 : 5 HCl. The residual iron was further masked with NH₄F and the vanadium content in the solution was determined by taking suitable aliquot of the dilute solution using the recommended procedure.

The results of analysis of some standard steel samples are presented in Table 1. Results obtained by estimating vanadium with PAR reagent are given within brackets. The values obtained with the two reagents agree well.

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TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN BCS STEELS

Sample of steel	Vanadium content		% Deviation
	Found*	Certified value	
258/1	0.335 (0.340)	0.35	- 4.28
481	0.53 (0.54)	0.52	+ 1.92
410/1	0.24 (0.245)	0.23	+ 4.34

*Average of three determinations.

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Extraction-Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Copper(II) with Diphenylcarbazone

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DIPHENYLCARBAZONE forms chelate complexes with a number of metal ions¹. Copper(II) reacts with this reagent forming a red coloured complex which is extractable into isobutyl methyl ketone. Seno and Kakita² used this reagent for the determination of copper. In the present investigation, a spectrophotometric method for determination of copper in micro amounts using diphenylcarbazone as reagent is described. The method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective.

Experimental

A Beckmann DK-2 spectrophotometer with quartz cuvettes of 1 cm thickness was used for absorbance measurements. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was measured with a pH meter.

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving 1.96 g $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double distilled water

containing a few drops of H_2SO_4 and was standardized by complexometric method³. The solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by dilution from the stock solution. A 0.02% solution of diphenylcarbazone (B.D.H.) in isobutyl methyl ketone was used as the reagent. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the metal salts or from the sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of anions. Adjustment of pH of the aqueous phase was made with 0.2 M sodium acetate-0.2 M acetic acid.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot of the dilute copper solution containing 0.5 to 14 μg copper was made up to 5 ml, the pH adjusted to 5.6 and was shaken with 10 ml of 0.02% solution of diphenylcarbazone in isobutyl methyl ketone for 3 min. The organic layer was separated and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 540 nm against a reagent blank. The amounts of copper in unknown solutions were calculated from a calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectrum of a solution of copper(II)-diphenylcarbazone complex in isobutyl methyl ketone (0.4 ppm copper) at pH 5.6 against a reagent blank is shown in Fig. 1A. The spectrum of the reagent blank vs the solvent is also shown in Fig. 1B. The maximum absorption of the complex is at 540 nm.

Effect of pH: The complex exhibited constant and maximum absorbance in the pH range 5.3 to 8.0. The effect of pH on the extraction of the complex is presented in Fig. 2. 0.5 to 14 μg copper

Fig. 1. A. Absorption spectrum of copper(II)-diphenylcarbazone complex in isobutyl methyl ketone (0.4 ppm Cu) against the reagent blank.

B. The spectrum of the reagent blank against the solvent.